

Systems Oriented Towards Inclusion and Psychosocial Risk Prevention in Industrial Psychology: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

Introduction: Work and organizational psychology plays a fundamental role in the context of inclusion and prevention of psychosocial risk. To date, however, these objectives are not yet fully achieved. Our goal, therefore, is to contribute to understanding the current gaps.

Methods: This scoping review followed the PRISMA guidelines and included evidence-based studies published from 2018 to 2023. This search was conducted across three scientific databases (Cochrane, Google Scholar, and Medline). All studies on inclusion and prevention programs designed in workplaces evaluating their psychological impact and written in English were included. The search took into consideration articles with the following terms: "Inclusion and Disability", "work-organizational psychology and disability", "Disability and LGBTQ+ intersectionality", "Microaggression and Disability", "Sexism and Gender Equality", "Disability and Inclusive Language", "Requirements risks and opportunities in Disabilities", "Ableism and Disability", "Organizational Well-being and Disability", "Psychological Competence and Disability", "Disability Studies and Psychology", "Gender Equality in the Workplace", "Sexism and Racism".

Results: The search strategy generated 999 results; 58 articles were included after screening. From the analyses carried out, it emerged, therefore, how organizational psychologists can play a fundamental role in promoting and accepting these instances.

Discussion: Working on positive factors, such as communication and cooperation, as well as the presence of organizational support and efficient stress management, can reduce the biopsychosocial risk.

Keywords: Disability; Diversity; Inclusion; Organizational Psychology; Psychosocial Risk Prevention.

Cite this paper as: Giorgi G, El Alami L, Khabbache H, Rizzo A. Systems Oriented Towards Inclusion and Psychosocial Risk Prevention in Industrial Psychology: A Scoping Review..Adv Med Psychol Public Health. 2026;3(2):133-151. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18048482.

Received: 10 January 2025; Revised: 15 May 2025; Accepted: 10 December 2025; Published Online: 24 December 2025

INTRODUCTION

The value of professional psychology practice in organizational settings is widely recognized. For years, scientific literature has produced evidence supporting the effectiveness of psychologically based interventions in businesses [1-3]. However, the contribution of professional psychologists in work settings that include organizational actors characterized by different abilities, cultures, religions, genders, and ages has been less considered, only gaining attention in the recent scientific literature [4,5].

We live in a period of significant change; although these changes began some time ago (e.g., Globalization, Industry 4.0), their effects are now profoundly felt [6-9]. Other historical events have also significantly impacted this scenario; the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has acted as an accelerator for some changes that would otherwise have taken more time while simultaneously highlighting personal and social inequalities among workers in a disruptive and forceful manner [10-12].

Social, economic, and geopolitical changes have weakened the relationship between workers and employers, making the purely legal-contractual bond increasingly precarious motivation managed solely through schedules, pay, and benefits. In the face of job instability, companies need to develop new methods to promote motivation, productivity, development, and employee well-being. Senior management figures will be crucial in inclusion processes [13]. Over recent decades, scientific literature shifted its focus toward business leaders' social and cross-functional skills, moving from a purely transactional paradigm to a transformative paradigm [14]. Inclusion management capable of creating "beneficial" and inclusive leadership has been linked to higher levels of organizational well-being and improved job performance [15-17]. The perceived equity by staff and the perception of organizational justice will also be paramount [18,19], especially within the highly prominent context of gender equality today [20]. It has also been observed how social, cultural, and religious influences [21] can modify gender inequality perceptions, promoting an ideal of "beneficial inequality" and justifying differences in pay and social status at work. Justice, support, and organizational climate can positively correlate with commitment, performance, and job well-being. It is thus important to discuss the inclusion of diversity and ensure operations within an organizational context perceived as fair, where everyone has the same opportunities regardless of personal, cultural, and individual characteristics.

This scoping review aims to investigate and analyze the relationship between organizations and psychological best practices to evaluate their effectiveness in inclusion and psychosocial risk prevention. This study will focus on the

organizational business context, thereby excluding research sets in clinical and/or educational settings from the discussion.

To understand the scope and impact on the affected workers, this review will specifically consider the class of workers with disabilities protected under Legislative Decree 88/99; according to ISTAT data collected by the observatory in 2021, 40.9% of employees in Italy have severe or mild limitations, while 15.1% of job seekers have severe or mild limitations [22].

METHODS

Search strategy and study selection

This scoping review followed the PRISMA guidelines [23] and included evidence-based studies published from 2018 to 2023. The following terms were included in searches across three scientific databases, including the Cochrane Library, Google Scholar, and Medline (PubMed): 'Inclusion and Disability', 'Work-organizational psychology and disability', 'Disability and LGBTQ+ intersectionality', 'Microaggression and Disability', 'Sexism and Gender Equality', 'Disability and Inclusive Language', 'Requirements risks and opportunities in Disabilities', 'Ableism and Disability', 'Organizational Well-being and Disability', 'Psychological Competence and Disability', 'Disability Studies and Psychology', 'Gender Equality in the Workplace', 'Sexism and Racism'. The article selection process was conducted in three stages, screening the articles by title and abstract and then by full text. In the first stage, relevant studies based on their title were excluded. In the second stage, studies without intervention that reported on conference papers or provided generic data on the topic of disability or that reported results of empirical research but without intervention programs implemented in the workplace were excluded. In the third stage, full texts were considered admissible if they reported on work and organizational psychology initiatives on inclusion-focused interventions and were available with an evaluation of psychological outcomes.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were as follows: the study involved the analysis of programs on the theme of work psychology applied to developing systems oriented towards inclusion and the prevention of psychosocial risk. Thus, cohort studies (study design) were deemed admissible if they concerned intervention initiatives such as inclusion, diversity, and disability for the working population (study population) and were conducted in the workplace (setting), provided they reported an evaluation of the intervention's effectiveness from a psychological viewpoint (outcome). Articles in languages other than English, conference proceedings, and publications for which the full text was not available were excluded.

Data extraction

A standard format was used to report the first author's year of publication and describe the objectives, context, participants, methods, and main results highlighted in the studies. Missing information is noted as unavailable.

Synthesis and Analysis of Results

The data presented were analyzed, including the psychological approach undertaken, the timing of the measures of psychological variables collected in the studies, and the statistical analyses performed on the collected data. The participants' characteristics include gender, age, race/ethnicity, professional category, and inclusion criteria, if available. The analysis of articles based on the characteristics of the intervention was conducted, taking into account the intervention approaches derived from work psychology aimed at developing and enhancing inclusion and inclusivity in the workplace, as well as the duration of the intervention, any dropouts, and the planning of follow-ups to assess its effectiveness. Finally, the main results obtained from the interventions concerning the achieved objectives were summarized.

RESULTS

The search strategy generated 999 indexed research outputs in the databases selected for this study, with no duplicate

records. In addition to off-topic articles (n=400) excluded based on their titles, 599 studies were initially selected. 300 were excluded based on their abstracts, and 100 were conference papers. Further screening excluded 35 studies for non-significant results, 50 for not aligning with intervention approaches derived from work and organizational psychology, and another 50 for not being relevant to the themes of inclusion and disability. In total, 64 peer-reviewed full-text documents were included in the review. The flow diagram of the selection process is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram showing the study inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Study characteristics

Regarding the types of articles included in this review (see Table 1), 23 articles report analyses of the scientific literature, focusing on key studies related to inclusion within organizational contexts [6,10,15,18,22,24,27,34,41]. These cover issues such as the perception of organizational justice concerning gender diversity [4,30], the lacking inclusion of women in the workplace [21,39], the promotion of human rights and equity in healthcare [35,45], as well as the investigation into work ability [13,29] and the impact of the SARS-CoV-2 virus on these categories [11,28,42,75]. Abbott’s [1] study highlights how the use of inclusive language can enhance communication quality, thereby facilitating the setting of future sustainable development goals [52].

The remaining 41 articles involved experimental investigations on topics such as disability [2,6,9,10,16,19,25,40,49], inclusion [50,51], LGBT+ [43], ethnicity [12,48], sex [5,44,63], gender equity [4,17,19,22,37], and religion [21]. Many of these studies were conducted in Europe [64,71] and America [3,15], within organizational and corporate settings [48,60]. Some studies employed online survey methodologies [20,23,63].

Table 1. Summary of studies included in the scoping review (n = 58).

First Author, Year of Publication	Study design	Country	Target population/ Setting	Aims/findings of the study
Haggard MC [20]	Experimental survey with four experiments	Belgium and the United States	Catholics, Protestants, atheists, theists	Explored how exposure to religious concepts can increase self-reported benevolent sexism.
Sundar V [22]	National Randomized Telephone Survey	United States	Over 3000 adults with disabilities or their family members	Examined personal and organizational predictors of job satisfaction among American workers with disabilities.
Patras L [23]	Training and questionnaire distribution	Not specified	885 employees and 809 families of individuals with intellectual disabilities across 104 organizations	Explored the role of climate as a mediator between employees' beliefs about "helping others" and organizational performance focused on quality of life.
Zhu X [24]	Questionnaire administered in two stages	China (Northern)	757 respondents in 114 teams across two manufacturing companies	Explored the interaction between employee disability and team inclusion and learning
Bogart KR [25]	Literature review	Not applicable	General	Analyzed and critiqued the concept of ableism in society.
Coleman JS [19]	Workplace analysis during 2010 and 2011	Not specified	60 women in their fifties from advertising, medicine, surgery, and school administration	Highlighted obstacles for women toward leadership and the entrenched male work culture.
Cavero-Rubio JA [26]	Survey with multivariate analysis	Spain	Sample of 22 randomly selected companies	Studied the impact of a gender equality distinction on companies' financial performance.
Kaggwa M [27]	Interviews, market research, literature review	South Africa (various locations)	Black women in the mining sector	This study explored the challenges still faced by women in the workplace despite progressive gender regulations.
Dirth TP [28]	Online survey, regression analysis, mediation analysis	Conducted online	Participants recruited from Amazon's Mechanical Turk	This study identified socio-psychological factors that may promote (or inhibit) the perception of discrimination as illegitimate among people with disabilities.
Edgelow MM [29]	Systematic literature analysis	Not applicable	General	Identified and described occupational therapy interventions for return to work in cases of trauma and stress-related disorders.

Coe IR [30]	Systematic literature analysis	Not applicable	General, with a focus on women in science and medicine	Discussed issues related to the underrepresentation of women in science and medicine, highlighting actions, tools, techniques, and solutions that could lead to gender equity.
Baker M [31]	Data analysis from archives	Not specified	358 organizations	Tested a positive relationship between gender equality initiatives and female representation at both managerial and non-managerial levels; examined the moderating effect of women in top management teams on this relationship.
Woods M [32]	Systematic literature analysis	Not applicable	General, with emphasis on individuals with mental illnesses	Explored how workplace experiences impact mental health, emphasizing the social suffering experienced by people with mental illnesses in work settings.
Chawla S [33]	Staff survey	India	433 managers (201 women and 233 men) from private-sector companies	Determined the role of psychological capital and perceived gender equity, assessing whether commitment and social support mediate the relationship between these factors and well-being.
Luu TT [16]	Multilevel structural equation modeling analysis	Vietnam (Ho Chi Minh City)	502 employees with disabilities from 98 departments across 67 companies	Examined how benevolent leadership contributes to the well-being of employees with disabilities, focusing on the impact of such leadership on work and personal resources.
Perrin PB [34]	Literature analysis	Not applicable	General, focusing on individuals with disabilities	Introduced a special issue of 'Rehabilitation Psychology' on diversity and social justice in disability research, highlighting a holistic psychosocial perspective encompassing all aspects of disability.
Birau FR [35]	Empirical research using labor market microdata	Romania	Unemployed individuals with disabilities	Identified variables significantly affecting employment risk exit in the Romanian labor market. Noted longer unemployment duration for specific categories of disabled individuals, examining factors like gender, age, education, area of residence, and previous work experience.

Bonaccio S [36]	Literature reviews, data analysis, and synthesis of existing research	Not specified	Individuals with disabilities either seeking employment or currently employed, and employers concerned about hiring and working with disabled individuals	Addressed common employer concerns about employees with disabilities, contributing to the creation of more effective, equitable, and inclusive workplaces.
Kamasak R [6]	Thematic analysis of qualitative interview data	Turkey	11 LGBTQ+ adults	Explored intersectionality at the individual and institutional levels, discussing how intersectionality manifests as forms of solidarity and hostility in the workplace.
Coron C [37]	Mixed-methods approach combining a quantitative survey and qualitative study	France	Employees in a French company	Investigated social representations of gender equality at work, how these definitions influence policy implementation.
Gillovic B [38]	Literature review	Not applicable	General, focusing on the tourism industry	Emphasized the need for more accessible and inclusive tourism, proposing a conceptual approach based on seven elements of inclusive tourism
Krieger N [39]	Literature review	Not applicable	General, with focus on social inequalities	Analyzed intersections of racism, sexism, heterosexism, and gender binarism using an ecosocial theory, discussing how injustice impacts health and promoting human rights and health equity.
Bae J [40]	Systematic Literature review	Not applicable	General, with focus on gender research in management	Aimed to invigorate gender research in management by consolidating insights from a positive workplace perspective
Molero F [41]	Structural Equation Modeling	Spain	288 Spanish participants with varying degrees of physical disabilities	Analyzed the consequences of discrimination on self-esteem among physically disabled individuals, finding different impacts of personal versus group perceived discrimination.
Annaswamy TM [42]	Comprehensive Analysis	Not specified	Disabled individuals using telemedicine services	Explored barriers and opportunities in using telemedicine for healthcare among disabled individuals, focusing on accessibility and inclusivity.
Brook F [43]	In-depth Interviews	Not specified	55 women in library leadership roles	Examined female leadership in libraries through interviews, contributing insights into leadership dynamics in library environments.

Figueredo J-M [44]	Systematic literature review	Not applicable	Not specified	Identified common psychosocial factors predicting subjective and psychological well-being in return-to-work (RTW) processes after health issues or long-term disability.
Grant B [45]	Meta-analysis using the "job demands-resources" model, combined with primary data collection	Not specified	Not specified	Analyzed the concept of Work Ability (WA) to support older workers, those with disabilities, or mental health issues, emphasizing WA's value for future research and practices.
Hideg I [46]	Literature review focused on 21st-century publications in industrial and organizational psychology	Not specified	Not specified	Reviewed gender equality research to promote further awareness and change, discussing the need for greater female inclusion in leadership as a social responsibility.
Shi X [47]	Online survey	China	507 female workers	Examined whether feminist identity affects perceptions and tolerance of sexual harassment, mediating the relationships between sexism, gender roles, and perceived and tolerated harassment.
Rathmann K [48]	Online study involving both quantitative and qualitative analysis	Germany	130 staff and managers in facilities for disabled individuals	Employed the "Health literate health care organization scale" (HLHO-10) to quantitatively measure and qualitatively define organizational health literacy characteristics.
Marina R [49]	Descriptive analysis with bivariate correlations, moderation tested via macro process	Spain	245 disabled employees, mostly women, with an average age of 41.5 years	Explored how job satisfaction affects company turnover among employees with disabilities, including the moderating effects of various types of organizational commitment.
Camisa V [50]	Experimental design with multiple levels of analysis	Italy	131 healthcare workers, 89.7% women, average age 50.4 years	Evaluated a workplace disability management program, employing descriptive, t-test, Mann-Whitney U test, chi-square test, and economic analysis.
Wenham C [51]	Literature review	Not specified	Not specified	Reviewed gender roles before and after COVID-19, mainly focusing on the impact of remote work.
Eikhof DR [52]	Literature review	Not specified	Not specified	Combined pre-COVID research with emerging industry policies to identify key impacts on inclusive practices and workforce participation during cultural change.

Madera JM [53]	Between-groups factorial experiment	Not specified	370 participants recruited via Amazon Mechanical Turk	Examined whether an employee's disability status affects customer service evaluations.
Foley M [54]	Observational and literature analysis	Not specified	Not specified	Investigated the impact of the pandemic on female employment, workforce participation, earnings, and experiences of gender-based violence.
Maria Szulc J [55]	Literature review	Not specified	Not specified	Proposed greater attention to neurodivergent employees and integration of policies for managing neurodiversity, highlighting it as an overlooked area in management research.
Moser CE [56]	Series of studies with integrated data analysis	Not specified	Predominantly women in male-dominated industries	Explored the impact of male allies on reducing harmful effects of gender underrepresentation, examining how race and gender of both participants and allies influence perceptions.
Jammaers E [57]	Case study	Not specified	BankCorp with 15,000 employees	Analyzed how ableism acts as a form of symbolic violence, limiting career opportunities for disabled employees in a financial services company.
Jansen J [15]	Literature review focusing on employer characteristics related to workforce participation	Not specified	Not specified	Explored employer characteristics associated with the work participation of people with disabilities and chronic illnesses.
Tomczak MT [58]	Qualitative study with expert interviews	Not specified	Therapists, trainers, and entrepreneurs employing autistic individuals	Analyzed how communication processes in recruitment, selection, and retention could be modified to meet the specific needs of people on the autism spectrum.
Bartram T [59]	Case study involving interviews, focus groups, and observations	Australia	Three hotels, a courier company, a film company, a management consulting firm, and a recruitment agency	Explored the impact of human resource management on workers with intellectual disabilities across various sectors, aiming to identify management strategies for handling intellectual disability.

Gappmayer G [60]	Observational study with vignettes	Not specified	Researcher and Herbert, a young man with Down syndrome	Provided a deeper understanding of occupations through the study of ableism and disableism, discussing how social norms about being able to affect human interactions and produce differences among people.
Chung H [61]	Online survey	UK	560 heterosexual parents with children under 18	Explored the role of flexible work for gender equality during the COVID-19 pandemic among workers surveyed during the first lockdown via Twitter and Facebook.
Tiago SJ [62]	Literature analysis	Not specified	Not specified	Assessed the impact of COVID-19 on people with disabilities, with a focus on negative occupational, socioeconomic, and health outcomes.
Salter NP [63]	Analysis of archival data	Not specified	6,000 employees from various organizations	Examined how holding multiple minority statuses affects work experiences and attitudes.
Burns KEA [64]	Cross-sectional survey	Not specified	400 physicians	Evaluated the impact of organizational culture on professional achievement and burnout among physicians.
Parmer LL [65]	Data analysis focusing on women	USA	Not specified	Examined persistent barriers that American women face in the workplace, such as gender biases and stereotypes, and assessed the impact of the pandemic on women's employment, workforce participation, earnings, and experiences of gender violence
Bourabain D [66]	Semi-structured face-to-face interviews	Belgium	Five public universities: majority ethnic (EMAW) and minority ethnic (EMIW) women, including doctoral and post-doctoral researchers	Investigated the "leaky pipeline" where the representation of women and people of color decreases at higher academic levels, largely due to structural barriers like hiring and recruitment practices.
Chadwick D [67]	Two-step design involving a rapid review and an international study	International (based on author origins)	Not specified	Addressed how the shift from online to offline daily activities during COVID-19 affected people with intellectual disabilities.
Dill J [68]	Observational and literature review	USA	Black women	Described how structural racism and sexism shape the occupational trajectories of Black women in the U.S. healthcare system.
Maltezou HC [69]	Cross-sectional survey	China	2,030 healthcare workers (hospitals)	Studied the relationship between shoulder/neck pain and both individual and organizational variables.

Moser CE [56]	Experimental study with integrated data analysis	Not specified	Not specified	Investigated whether commitment from dominant group members to allyship conveys safety to women in male-dominated environments. The study used a series of experiments to assess women's perceptions of workplace safety with or without the presence of male allies and the impact of a female ally in one scenario.
Tortia EC [70]	Descriptive and confirmatory factor analysis	Italy	4,134 workers in 310 non-profit social enterprises	Discussed the challenges and opportunities for sustainable human resource management (HRM) practices in the care services sector. The study highlighted the impact of these practices on organizational performance, including service quality and organizational innovation.
Abbott MRB [71]	Literature review	Not specified	Not specified	Provided an overview of inclusive language and conducted a comparative textual analysis. Emphasized the importance of respectful communication in healthcare settings and outlined preferred language protocols as identified by various national organizations.
Vermiglio C [72]	Theoretical analysis	Not specified	Women with disabilities	Analyzed gender equality within the sustainable development goals framework with a specific focus on the tourism and hospitality industry. Addressed the substantial neglect and marginalization of people with disabilities, particularly women, in discussions on tourism.

Meyer I [73]	Review	Not specified	Not specified	Described how the field of psychology, particularly through the journal 'International Perspectives in Psychology', is significantly contributing to achieving the SDGs. The text highlights how understanding indigenous psychological constructs and methodologies in various regions can lead to innovative solutions to pressing humanitarian issues, including adjustments in aggression assessment scales across cultures and the psychological experience during the COVID-19 pandemic.
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DISCUSSION

This review has demonstrated how the issues of prejudice and discrimination remain pervasive in organizational contexts. It has also highlighted that the role of the work and organizational psychologist can be crucial in creating work environments that promote the well-being of both individuals and groups [17]. Specifically, this article analyzed aspects related to gender equity, and various studies have shown that the principle of equity between men and women is not yet guaranteed in organizational settings [21,22]. Discrimination has also occurred in other areas such as ethnic background, sexual orientation, and the presence of visible or invisible disabilities [77]. In the field of inclusion and diversity, there are many themes and areas to manage for greater promotion.

Currently, organizational contexts are undergoing a true cultural revolution regarding how differences in ethnicity, race, culture, gender, and sexual orientation are perceived. This revolution has been driven in part by processes of globalization and digitalization [6,7,9]. Emerging phenomena related to the global response to the recent SARS-CoV-2 pandemic have undoubtedly accelerated and influenced these processes. The pandemic has led to an exponential increase in social interaction mediated by digital connectivity, which in turn has caused many to search for new work-life balances [28,75]. It has been noted that this increase in loneliness has particularly affected minorities who are not equitably represented in organizational settings, leading these groups to feelings of inadequacy and non-belonging in their companies [12,20,42].

In this context, the role of the work and organizational psychologist is paramount, contributing positively to inclusion through the development of programs such as "diversity-oriented" and "diversity, equity, and inclusion" initiatives [52]. Therefore, it is the task of the work psychologist to develop valuable resources for organizations, such as communication and cooperation, the perception of support from colleagues and superiors in work groups, and effective management of work-related stress, all of which can significantly influence the reduction of biopsychosocial risk for categories most at risk of vulnerability and marginalization in the workplace [19,22,45,52,53,78].

Study limitations

This scoping review presents some limitations. First, the exclusion of research sets in clinical and educational settings may limit the breadth of understanding regarding the application of psychological best practices across different sectors. Moreover, while the search strategy was comprehensive, it is possible that some relevant studies were missed due to the limitations of search terms or database indexing. Additionally, the review focused on a limited timeframe (2018-2023), which may have excluded earlier seminal works in the field of organizational psychology and inclusion.

Implications for policymakers

Policymakers should recognize the importance of creating inclusive work environments that accommodate diversity in terms of gender, ethnicity, ability, and other individual characteristics. This review highlights the significant role organizational psychologists play in developing interventions to foster inclusive workplaces [79-87]. Therefore, it is essential to support research and development in this area, along with implementing policies that promote equity and inclusion. Policymakers should consider mandating certain psychological and organizational well-being practices, particularly for vulnerable groups, to ensure their fair treatment and well-being in the workplace.

CONCLUSIONS

The review confirms that inclusive practices and diversity management in organizational settings have a profound impact on worker well-being, particularly for those from marginalized or minority groups. Work and organizational psychologists play a pivotal role in promoting these initiatives, thereby fostering both individual and collective well-being. Further research is needed to explore the effectiveness of these interventions in diverse settings and populations, and policies must evolve to support more inclusive and equitable workplace environments.

Author Contributions : Conceptualization: G.G.; methodology: G.G. and L.E.A.; validation: G.G. and A.R.; formal analysis: L.E.A. and H.K.; resources: H.K.; data curation: L.E.A.; writing—original draft preparation: L.E.A. and H.K.; writing—review and editing: G.G. and A.R.; supervision: G.G. and A.R. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgments: None.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

1. Gelfand MJ, Aycan Z, Erez M, Leung K. Cross-cultural industrial organizational psychology and organizational behavior: a hundred-year journey. *J Appl Psychol.* 2017;102(3):514–529. doi:10.1037/apl0000186.
2. Ochoa Pacheco P, Coello-Montecel D, Tello M. Psychological empowerment and job performance: examining serial mediation effects of self-efficacy and affective commitment. *Adm Sci.* 2023;13(3):76. doi:10.3390/admsci13030076.
3. Raquel RC, Bernardo MJ, Sara DR-H, Abraham Á-B, Ana IS-V. Positive psychology at work: mutual gains for individuals and organizations. *Rev Psicol Trab Organ.* 2010;26(3):235–253. doi:10.5093/tr2010v26n3a7.
4. Nguyen NTH, Tuan LT. Trust in multilevel managers and employee extra-role behavior in the US federal government: the role of psychological well-being and workload. *Rev Public Pers Adm.* 2022;42(2):312–337. doi:10.1177/0734371X20979683.
5. Shore LM, Randel AE, Chung BG, Dean MA, Holcombe Ehrhart K, Singh G. Inclusion and diversity in work groups: a review and model for future research. *J Manag.* 2011;37(4):1262–1289. doi:10.1177/0149206310385943.
6. Kamasak R, Ozbilgin M, Baykut S, Yavuz M. Moving from intersectional hostility to intersectional solidarity: insights from LGBTQ individuals in Turkey. *J Organ Change Manag.* 2019;33(3):456–476. doi:10.1108/JOCM-11-2018-0328.
7. Lee Y-T, Gyamfi NY. Multicultural identities at work. In: *Oxford research encyclopedia of business and management.* Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2023. doi:10.1093/acrefore/9780190224851.013.351.
8. Wang X, Sun Y, Ding D. Adaptive dynamic programming for networked control systems under communication constraints: a survey of trends and techniques. *Int J Netw Dyn Intell.* 2022;1(1):85–98. doi:10.53941/ijndi0101008.
9. Wang Y, Byrne L, Bartram T, Chapman M. Developing inclusive and healthy organizations by employing designated lived experience

- roles: learning from human resource management innovations in the mental health sector. *Int J Hum Resour Manag.* 2023;34(10):1973–2001. doi:10.1080/09585192.2022.2054287.
10. Baldassarre A, Giorgi G, Alessio F, Lulli LG, Arcangeli G, Mucci N. Stigma and discrimination (SAD) at the time of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(17):6341. doi:10.3390/ijerph17176341.
 11. Foti G, Bondanini G, Finstad GL, Alessio F, Giorgi G. The relationship between occupational stress, mental health and COVID-19-related stress: mediation analysis results. *Adm Sci.* 2023;13(4):116. doi:10.3390/admsci13040116.
 12. Giorgi G, Lecca LI, Alessio F, Finstad GL, Bondanini G, Lulli LG, et al. COVID-19-related mental health effects in the workplace: a narrative review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(21):7857.
 13. Kuknor SC, Bhattacharya S. Inclusive leadership: new age leadership to foster organizational inclusion. *Eur J Train Dev.* 2022;46(9):771–797. doi:10.1108/EJTD-07-2019-0132.
 14. Bass BM. From transactional to transformational leadership: learning to share the vision. *Organ Dyn.* 1990;18(3):19–31. doi:10.1016/0090-2616(90)90061-S.
 15. Jansen J, Van Ooijen R, Koning PWC, Boot CRL, Brouwer S. The role of the employer in supporting work participation of workers with disabilities: a systematic literature review using an interdisciplinary approach. *J Occup Rehabil.* 2021;31(4):916–949. doi:10.1007/s10926-021-09978-3.
 16. Luu TT. Building employees' organizational citizenship behavior for the environment: the role of environmentally-specific servant leadership and a moderated mediation mechanism. *Int J Contemp Hosp Manag.* 2019;31(1):406–426. doi:10.1108/IJCHM-07-2017-0425.
 17. Beloskar VD, Halidar A, Gupta A. Gender equality and women's empowerment: a bibliometric review of the literature on SDG 5 through the management lens. *J Bus Res.* 2024;172:114442. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.114442.
 18. Gupta V, Mittal S, Ilavarasan PV, Budhwar P. Pay-for-performance, procedural justice, OCB and job performance: a sequential mediation model. *Pers Rev.* 2024;53(1):136–154. doi:10.1108/PR-11-2021-0782.
 19. Coleman JS. *Equality and achievement in education.* Routledge; 2019.
 20. Haggard MC, Kaelen R, Saroglou V, Klein O, Rowatt WC. Religion's role in the illusion of gender equality: supraliminal and subliminal religious priming increases benevolent sexism. *Psychol Relig Spiritual.* 2019;11(4):392–398. doi:10.1037/rel0000196.
 21. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ.* 2021;372. doi:10.1136/bmj.n71.
 22. Sundar V, O'Neill J, Houtenville AJ, Phillips KG, Keirns T, Smith AE, et al. Striving to work and overcoming barriers: employment strategies and successes of people with disabilities. *J Vocat Rehabil.* 2018;48(1):93–109. doi:10.3233/JVR-170918.
 23. Pătraș L, Martínez-Tur V, Estreder Y, Gracia E, Moliner C, Peiró JM. Organizational performance focused on users' quality of life: the role of service climate and "contribution-to-others" well-being beliefs. *Res Dev Disabil.* 2018;77:114–123. doi:10.1016/j.ridd.2018.04.016.
 24. Zhu X, Law KS, Sun C, Yang D. Thriving of employees with disabilities: the roles of job self-efficacy, inclusion, and team-learning climate. *Hum Resour Manag.* 2019;58(1):21–34. doi:10.1002/hrm.21920.
 25. Bogart KR & Dunn DS. Ableism Special Issue Introduction. *J Soc Issues.* 2019;75(3):650–664. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12354>.
 26. Cavero-Rubio JA, Collazo-Mazón A, Amorós-Martínez A. Public recognition of gender equality in the workplace and its influence on firms' performance. *Women's Stud Int Forum.* 2019;76:102273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2019.102273>.
 27. Kaggwa M. Interventions to promote gender equality in the mining sector of South Africa. *Extr Ind Soc.* 2020;7(2):398–404. doi:10.1016/j.exis.2019.03.015.
 28. Dirth TP, Branscombe NR. Recognizing ableism: a social identity analysis of disabled people perceiving discrimination as illegitimate. *J Soc Issues.* 2019;75(3):786–813. doi:10.1111/josi.12345.
 29. Edgelow MM, MacPherson MM, Arnaly F, Tam-Seto L, Cramm HA. Occupational therapy and posttraumatic stress disorder: A

- scoping review. *Can J Occup Ther.* 2019;86(2):148–157. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008417419831438>.
30. Coe IR, Wiley R, Bekker L-G. Organisational best practices towards gender equality in science and medicine. *Lancet.* 2019;393(10171):587–593. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(18)33188-X.
 31. Baker M, Ali M, French E. Effectiveness of gender equality initiatives in project-based organizations in Australia. *Aust J Manag.* 2019;44(3):425–442. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0312896218805809>.
 32. Woods M, Macklin R, Dawkins S, Martin A. Mental illness, social suffering and structural antagonism in the labour process. *Work Employ Soc.* 2019;33(6):948–965. doi:10.1177/0950017019866650.
 33. Chawla S, Sharma RR. Enhancing women’s well-being: the role of psychological capital and perceived gender equity, with social support as a moderator and commitment as a mediator. *Front Psychol.* 2019;10:1377. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01377.
 34. Perrin PB. Diversity and social justice in disability: The heart and soul of rehabilitation psychology. *Rehabil Psychol.* 2019;64(2):105–110. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rep0000278>.
 35. Birau FR., Dănaică DE, Spulbar CM. Social Exclusion and Labor Market Integration of People with Disabilities. A Case Study for Romania. *Sustainability.* 2019;11(18):5014. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11185014>.
 36. Bonaccio S, Lapierre LM, O’Reilly J. Creating work climates that facilitate and maximize the benefits of disclosing mental health problems in the workplace. *Organ Dyn.* 2019;48(3):113–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2019.03.006>.
 37. Coron C. What does “gender equality” mean? Social representations of gender equality in the workplace among French workers. *Equal Divers Incl.* 2020;39(8):825–847. doi:10.1108/EDI-06-2019-0185.
 38. Gillovic B, McIntosh A. Accessibility and inclusive tourism development: current state and future agenda. *Sustainability.* 2020;12(22):9722. doi:10.3390/su12229722.
 39. Krieger N. Measures of racism, sexism, heterosexism, and gender binarism for health equity research: from structural injustice to embodied harm—an ecosocial analysis. *Annu Rev Public Health.* 2020;41(1):37–62. doi:10.1146/annurev-publhealth-040119-094017.
 40. Bae J, Jennings PF, Hardeman CP, Kim E, Lee M, Littleton T, et al. Compassion Satisfaction Among Social Work Practitioners: The Role of Work–Life Balance. *J Soc Serv Res.* 2020;46(3):320–330. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01488376.2019.1566195>.
 41. Molero F, Recio P, Sarriá E. Living space and job prospects and their relationship with subjective well-being during COVID-19 confinement in Spain: the mediator role of resilience. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18(17):9198. doi:10.3390/ijerph18179198.
 42. Annaswamy TM, Verdusco-Gutierrez M, Frieden L. Telemedicine barriers and challenges for persons with disabilities: COVID-19 and beyond. *Disabil Health J.* 2020;13(4):100973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dhjo.2020.100973>.
 43. Brook F, Hallerduff M. Feminists at work: organizational leadership in academic libraries. In: Hines SS, Ketchum DH, editors. *Advances in library administration and organization.* Emerald Publishing Limited; 2020. p. 41–64. doi:10.1108/S0732-067120200000041004.
 44. Figueredo JM, García-Ael C, Gragnano A, Topa G. Well-being at work after return to work (RTW): a systematic review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(20):7490. doi:10.3390/ijerph17207490.
 45. Brady GM, Truxillo DM, Cadiz DM, Rineer JR, Caughlin DE, Bodner T. Opening the black box: examining the nomological network of work ability and its role in organizational research. *J Appl Psychol.* 2020;105(6):637–670. doi:10.1037/apl0000454.
 46. Hideg I, Wilson AE. History backfires: Reminders of past injustices against women undermine support for workplace policies promoting women. *Organ Behav Hum Decis Process.* 2020;156:176–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2019.10.001>.
 47. Shi X, Mao J, Liu Y. Pulp stem cells derived from human permanent and deciduous teeth: biological characteristics and therapeutic applications. *Stem Cells Transl Med.* 2020;9(4):445–464. doi:10.1002/sctm.19-0398.
 48. Rathmann K, Vockert T, Wetzel LD, Lutz J, Dadaczynski K. Organizational Health Literacy in Facilities for People with Disabilities: First Results of an Explorative Qualitative and Quantitative Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(8):2886. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17082886>.
 49. Romeo M, Yepes-Baldó M, Lins C. Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention Among People With Disabilities Working in Special

- Employment Centers: The Moderation Effect of Organizational Commitment. *Front Psychol.* 2020;11:1035.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01035>.
50. Camisa V, Gilardi F, Di Brino E, Santoro A, Vinci MR, Sannino S, et al. Return on investment (ROI) and development of a workplace disability management program in a hospital—a pilot evaluation study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(21):8084.
doi:10.3390/ijerph17218084.
51. Wenham C, Smith J, Morgan R. COVID-19: the gendered impacts of the outbreak. *Lancet.* 2020;395(10227):846–848.
doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30526-2.
52. Eikhof DR. COVID-19, inclusion and workforce diversity in the cultural economy: What now, what next? *Cult Trends.* 2020;29(3): 234–250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2020.1802202>.
53. Madera JM, Taylor DC, Barber NA. Customer Service Evaluations of Employees With Disabilities: The Roles of Perceived Competence and Service Failure. *Cornell Hosp Q.* 2020;61(1):5–18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1938965519882315>.
54. Foley M, Cooper R. Workplace gender equality in the post-pandemic era: where to next? *J Ind Relat.* 2021;63(4):463–476.
doi:10.1177/00221856211035173.
55. Szulc JM, McGregor FL, Cakir E. Neurodiversity and remote work in times of crisis: lessons for HR. *Pers Rev.* 2023;52(6):1677–1692.
doi:10.1108/PR-06-2021-0469.
56. Moser CE, Branscombe NR. Male allies at work: gender-equality supportive men reduce negative underrepresentation effects among women. *Soc Psychol Personal Sci.* 2022;13(2):372–381. doi:10.1177/19485506211033748.
57. Jammaers E, Zanoni P. The identity regulation of disabled employees: unveiling the ‘varieties of ableism’ in employers’ socio-ideological control. *Organ Stud.* 2021;42(3):429–452. doi:10.1177/0170840619900292.
58. Tomczak MT. Employees with autism spectrum disorders in the digitized work environment: perspectives for the future. *J Disabil Policy Stud.* 2021;31(4):195–205. doi:10.1177/1044207320919945.
59. Meacham H, Cavanagh J, Shaw A, Bartram T. HRM practices that support the employment and social inclusion of workers with an intellectual disability. *Pers Rev.* 2017;46(8):1475–1492. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-05-2016-0105>.
60. Gappmayer G. Disentangling disablism and ableism: The social norm of being able and its influence on social interactions with people with intellectual disabilities. *J Occup Sci.* 2021;28(1):102–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2020.1814394>.
61. Chung H, Birkett H, Forbes S, Seo H. Covid-19, Flexible Working, and Implications for Gender Equality in the United Kingdom. *Gend Soc.* 2021;35(2):218–232. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08912432211001304>.
62. Jesus T, Bhattacharjya S, Papadimitriou C, Bogdanova Y, Bentley J, Arango-Lasprilla JC, et al. Lockdown-related disparities experienced by people with disabilities during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic: scoping review with thematic analysis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18(12):6178. doi:10.3390/ijerph18126178.
63. Salter NP, Sasso T. The positive experiences associated with coming out at work. *Equal Divers Incl.* 2022;41(2):224–240.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/EDI-11-2020-0322>.
64. Burns KEA, Pattani R, Lorens E, Straus SE, Hawker GA. The impact of organizational culture on professional fulfillment and burnout in an academic department of medicine. *PLoS One.* 2021;16(6). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0252778.
65. Parmer LL. The road to gender equality: persisting obstacles for American women in the workforce. *Psychol Manag J.* 2021;24(2):85–96. doi:10.1037/mgr0000115.
66. Bourabain D. Everyday sexism and racism in the ivory tower: the experiences of early career researchers on the intersection of gender and ethnicity in the academic workplace. *Gend Work Organ.* 2021;28(1):248–267. doi:10.1111/gwao.12549.
67. Chadwick D, Ågren KA, Caton S, Chiner E, Danker J, Gómez-Puerta M, et al. Digital inclusion and participation of people with intellectual disabilities during COVID-19: a rapid review and international bricolage. *J Policy Pract Intellect Disabil.* 2022;19(3):242–256.
doi:10.1111/jppi.12410.
68. Dill J, Duffy M. Structural racism and Black women’s employment in the US health care sector: study examines structural racism and

- Black women's employment in the US health care sector. *Health Aff.* 2022;41(2):265–272. doi:10.1377/hlthaff.2021.01400.
69. Maltezou HC, Martínez-Jarreta B, Rapisarda V, Ledda C. Editorial: occupational risks of healthcare personnel. *Front Public Health.* 2022;10:1022327. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2022.1022327.
70. Tortia EC, Gago M, Degavre F, Poledrini S. Worker involvement and performance in Italian social enterprises: the role of motivations, gender and workload. *Sustainability.* 2022;14(2):1022. doi:10.3390/su14021022.
71. Abbott M. Finding the Right Words: Cohesion and Divergence in Inclusive Language Guidelines. *Online J Issues Nurs.* 2022;27(3). <https://doi.org/10.3912/OJIN.Vol27No03Man03>.
72. Vermiglio C, Naciti V, Noto G, Pulejo L. Gender and disabilities in the tourism industry. In: Abbate T, Cesaroni F, D'Amico A, editors. *Tourism and disability.* Springer International Publishing; 2022, pp. 103–114. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-93612-9_7.
73. Meyer IT, Teng-Calleja M, Mendiola M. International perspectives in psychology for sustainable life. *Int Perspect Psychol.* 2023. doi:10.1027/2157-3891/a000085.
74. Patel AV, Friedenreich CM, Moore SC, Hayes SC, Silver JK, Campbell KL, et al. American College of Sports Medicine roundtable report on physical activity, sedentary behavior, and cancer prevention and control. *Med Sci Sports Exerc.* 2019;51(11):2391–2402. doi:10.1249/MSS.0000000000002117.
75. Fine C, Sojo V. Women's value: beyond the business case for diversity and inclusion. *Lancet.* 2019;393(10171):515–516. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30165-5.
76. Gillovic B, McIntosh A. Accessibility and inclusive tourism development: current state and future agenda. *Sustainability.* 2020;12(22):9722. doi:10.3390/su12229722.
77. Molero F, Recio P, Sarriá E. Living space and job prospects and their relationship with subjective well-being during COVID-19 confinement in Spain: the mediator role of resilience. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18(17):9198. doi:10.3390/ijerph18179198.
78. Mark BG, Hofmayer S, Rauch E, Matt DT. Inclusion of Workers with Disabilities in Production 4.0: Legal Foundations in Europe and Potentials Through Worker Assistance Systems. *Sustainability.* 2019;11(21):5978. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11215978>.
79. Ait Ali D, Elhad H, Dihadril S, Ait Baja Z, Jaa M, Ali SA, et al. Assessing stress and reflective practice among nursing students during clinical practicum. *Teach Learn Nurs.* 2025 Jul 17.
80. Rizzo A, Laachi S, Ait Ali D, Khabbache H, Güler Öztekin G, Aksoy Ş, et al. The efficacy of emotional freedom techniques and tapping in reducing job stress and burnout: a review of research. *Mental Health Soc Incl.* 2025 May 9.
81. Di Stefano M, Barbera M, Bruno F, Foti C, Falliti F, Maggio MG, et al. Intervention of Snoezelen Rooms in reducing burnout among healthcare professionals: A pilot study. *G Ital Psicol Med Lav.* 2025;5(1):35–43.
82. García-Iglesias JJ, Chirico F, Rizzo A, Szarpak L, Khabbache H, Yildirim M, et al. Factors Influencing Occupational Stress of State Security Forces During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Scoping Review. *Risk Manag Healthc Policy.* 2024 Nov 20;17:2851.
83. Yildirim M, Akgül O, Geçer E, Bal F, Akgül O, Aziz Ia, et al. Covid-19 Impact and Job Satisfaction Among Mental Health Professionals: Mediating Roles Of Resilience And Social Connectedness. *TPM.* 2024 Dec 1;31(4).
84. Di Giampaolo L, Marino F, Giurgola C, Astolfi P, Coppeta L, De Sio S, et al. Mitigating overconfidence bias: A cross-sectional pilot study of male maintenance workers in the engineering sector. *J Health Soc Sci.* 2024;9(4):551-563.
85. Bondanini G, Giorgi G, Chirico F, Rizzo A, Khabbache H, Romana Testa F, et al. The relationship between discriminatory work environment and psychological distress in Italian organizations: Are lack of supervisor support and economic stress mediating factors? *J Health Soc Sci.* 2024;9(3):312-333.
86. Chmielewski J, Wojciechowska M, Chirico F, Crescenzo P, Rizzo A, Starz R, et al. Job burnout in a sample of Polish paramedics-role of work experience, age and health behaviours. *Ann Agric Environ Med.* 2024;31(3).
87. Qourrichi A, Ouazizi K, Saaliti E, Ait Ali D, El Alami L, Hilal M, et al. The effect of learned helplessness on the psychological health of healthcare workers. *J Health Soc Sci.* 2024;9(1):129-143.

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